

Wavelength dependent phototransformation of dibenzylideneacetonedibromide

Shivraj Singh Chawada^a, Suresh C. Ameta^b and Shubha Jain^{a*}

^aSchool of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain-456 010, India

E-mail : shivraj24@rediffmail.com

^bPhotochemistry & Solar Energy Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, M. L. Sukhadia University, Udaipur-313 002, India

Manuscript received 14 July 2003, accepted 11 June 2004

Dibenzylideneacetonedibromide (1) gives three different products 2, 3 and 4, when its solution in chloroform is irradiated by electromagnetic radiation at different wavelengths. The structures of these products have been confirmed by spectral analysis or co-TLC and mixed m.p. with authentic samples.

Photochemistry of a large number of carbonyl compounds has been investigated by various workers worldwide for last 30 years. The effect of various parameters like wavelength, intensity of light, nature of solvent, pH of the solution, nature of the light source etc. have been reported¹. Photochemistry of dibenzylideneacetonebromide at different wavelength of light used.

Results and discussion

Dibenzylideneacetonedibromide (1), when irradiated by visible light, underwent dimerization, giving the product 2 (Scheme 1). The IR spectrum (KBr) of product 2 gives absorption at (cm⁻¹) 3027.4 (arom. C-H stretch), 2990.5 (aliph. C-H stretch), 1732.1 (C=O stretch), 1597.2, 1454.2 (arom. ring stretch) and 637.2, 532.6 (C-Br stretch) etc. Its

Scheme 1

¹H NMR spectrum (in CDCl₃) gave signals at δ 7.1–7.4 (arom. protons), δ 5.7 (COCHBr protons), δ 5.5 (PhCHBr protons) and δ 3.8 and 4.1 (cyclobutane ring protons). Its ¹³C NMR spectrum gave signals at δ 198.9 (C=O carbon

atoms), 127–130 (arom. carbon atom), 51.4 (COCHBr carbon atoms), 48.7 (CHBrPh carbon atoms), 40.8 (CHCO carbon atoms) and 40.3 (CHPh carbon atoms). Its mass spectrum does not give the molecular ion peak, but gives the base peak at *m/z* 131. Other important peaks are observed at *m/z* 391, 312, 288, 260, 232, 103, 102, 77 etc. Presence of M+2 and M+4 peaks indicate the presence of bromine. The fragmentation pattern is given as :

Scheme 2

Upon irradiation by mercury vapour lamp ($\lambda \sim 360 \text{ nm}$), **1** underwent dimerization and debromination giving products **2** and **3** (Scheme 2). Product **3** has been confirmed as dibenzylideneacetone by co-TLC and mixed m.p. with the authentic sample. Whereas irradiation by UV light of wavelength $\sim 254 \text{ nm}$, **1** gave three products **2**, **3** and **4** (Scheme 3). The identification of products **2** and **3** has been done by co-TLC and mixed m.p. with the authentic samples and that of product **4** has been done by spectral analysis.

Scheme 3

IR spectrum (KBr) of product **4** shows important peaks at (cm^{-1}) 3029.8 (arom. C–H stretch), 2974.3 (aliph. C–H stretch), 1708.2 (C=O stretch), 1600.2 (arom. C=C ring stretch) etc. Its ^1H NMR spectrum shows peaks at δ 7.0–7.5 (arom. protons) and δ 3.8, 4.1 (alicyclic protons). The ^{13}C NMR spectrum of the product **4** shows absorption at δ 198.9 (carbonyl carbon atoms), 125–128 (arom. carbon atoms) and 47.7 and 49.2 (alicyclic carbon atoms). The mass spectrum of the product **4** shows the molecular ion peak at m/z 468 corresponding to the molecular weight of the product, base peak at m/z 131 and other important peaks at m/z 337, 234, 233, 206, 205, 180, 179, 178, 103, 77, 51 etc. The proposed fragmentation pattern may be given as :

Experimental

(i) *Preparation of dibenzylideneacetone (DBA)* : It was prepared from benzaldehyde and acetone using standard method².

(ii) *Preparation of dibenzylideneacetone dibromide (DBA dibromide)* : Dibenzylideneacetone (10 g) was dissolved in acetic acid (250 ml). This solution was then transferred to the three necked round bottomed flask attached with stirrer. The flask was kept in freezing mixture. Now a solution of bromine in acetic acid (10% v/v, 25 ml) was added dropwise through addition funnel at 0–5°C with stirring. The mixture was kept overnight, when the ppt of dibenzylideneacetone dibromide settled down. The resulting mass was filtered and was washed with cold water to eliminate excess acid and then it was recrystallized from

Table 1

Sl. no.	Type of irradiation	Time of irradiation (in h)	Product(s)	M.p. (°C)	Yields (~g)
1.	Visible	35	2	238	0.40
2.	UV light ($\lambda \sim 360$ nm)	20	2	238	0.80
			3	107	0.10
3.	UV light ($\lambda \sim 254$ nm)	10	2	238	0.90
			3	107	0.15
			4	116	0.10

ethanol to give white crystals of dibenzylideneacetone-dibromide (13 g, m.p. 163°).

(iii) *Photolysis of dibenzylideneacetone dibromide*: DBA dibromide (2 g) was dissolved in chloroform (200 ml). This solution was irradiated under different light sources viz. mercury vapour lamps ($\lambda \sim 360$ and 254 nm) and tungsten lamp (100 W). The progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC using benzene-hexane (4 : 1, v/v) as mobile phase. After completion of the reaction, solution was concentrated. The products were separated by preparative TLC and were recrystallized from ethanol. The m.p., yields and time of irradiation of the products are given in Table 1.

Conclusion :

Photolysis of organic compounds is affected by many factors e.g. wavelength, intensity of light source, nature of solvent, pH, temperature etc. Dibenzylideneacetone dibromide is found to be photochemically reactive by visible as well as UV light. At lower wavelength, the time of irradiation is less and yield and no. of products is more as com-

pared to higher wave length and visible light. This indicates that the rate of the reaction is affected by the energy of the source.

Acknowledgement

The author (S.S.C.) is indebted to Dr. Anindya Dutta, Visiting Scientist, Centre for Advance Technology (CAT), Indorc, Mr. Ajit Choubey, Factory Manager, Dr. B. K. Shrivastava, Asstt. Manager, R & D Department, IPCA Laboratories Ltd., Ratlam (M.P.) and authorities of R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow for providing spectral and elemental analysis data.

References

- G. Oster, M. Goodman and L. Citrarel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 703; T. Mukai, T. Oine and A. Malsubara, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1969, **42**, 581; E. R. Cole, G. Crank and E. Lye, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1978, **31**, 2675; K. C. Hwang, N. J. Turro and H. D. Roth, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1994, **59**, 1102; V. R. Gopal, A. M. Reddy and V. J. Rao, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1995, **60**, 7766; J. F. Lima and M. Y. Murakami Iha, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1996, **74**, 476; B. Singhal, A. Porwal, A. Sharma, R. Ameta and S. C. Ameta, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. Chem.*, 1997, **108**, 85; A. M. Gaber, I. Heise, J. Leitich and K. Schaffner, *J. Photochem. Photobiol. (A)*, 1999, **123**, 31; S. Jain and M. M. Bokadia, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1999, **38**, 232; A. Upadhyaya, M. M. Bokadia and S. Jain, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 97; B. Kheradia and S. Jain, *Nat. Acad. Sci. Lett.*, 2001, **24**, 13; S. Jain and S. S. Chawada, *Indian J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 2002, **11**, 247; S. S. Chawada, M. M. Bokadia and S. Jain, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2002, **41**, 865.
- A. I. Vogel, "Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry Including Qualitative Analysis", Longman Group Lit., London, 1978.